

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Second Cycle Evaluation Report

Deliverable number WP7_D7.4

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

Unless officially marked PUBLIC, this document and its contents remain the property of the beneficiaries of the WYRED Consortium and may not be distributed or reproduced without the express approval of the Project Coordinator.

H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2016

Grant Agreement number: 727066

1st November 2016 – 31st October 2019

Second Cycle Evaluation Report

Deliverable number WP7_D7.4

Deliverable description			
Filename	WYRED_WP7_D7.4.PDF		
Type	R		
Dissemination level	PU		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.3579342		
Due Date (in months)	M36		
Deliverable contributors			
Version No.	Name, Institution	Role	Last update
1	Paul Butler, PYE Global	author	16 /12 / 2019

* cfr. GA – Annex I Part A – 1.3.2 WT2 – list of deliverable

Table of contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Overview of Results	7
2.1 WYRED Activities in Cycle 3	7
2.2 Overview of Participant Numbers and Activities	9
2.3 Social Dialogues in Cycle 3	10
2.4 Research Work in Cycle 3	13
2.5 Interpretation and Analysis in Cycle 3	20
3. Analysis of WYRED Research Themes	22
3.1 Self-image and its presentation online	25
3.2 Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping	26
3.3 Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security	26
3.4 Living on social media, living with stress	28
3.5 Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy	30
3.6 Digital participation and activism, digital divide	31
4. Conclusions and Insights	33
4.1 Children and Young People in Control	33
4.2 WYRED Methodology as Empowerment	34
4.3 Completing a Body of Work	35
4.4 Educate and Legislate	36
Appendix 1: Research Questions Developed in Cycle 3	39
Appendix 2: Research Projects Developed in Cycle 3	43
References	46

1. Introduction

This report sets out to provide an interpretation of the results of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016, 2017; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) over its final cycle. Each cycle has involved the implementation and iteration of the WYRED methodological steps (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b, 2019). The third cycle has focused on learning key lessons and extracting insights for its sustainable and practical application.

The WYRED methodological approach involves a series of linked phases, beginning with a **consultation phase** involving outreach and engagement work and a social dialogue process. In this initial step, the children and young people are brought together and facilitated to examine digital society issues and concerns, using age appropriate facilitation techniques and tools. This work leads to a second **phase of research definition**. Through the articulation of research questions, the children and young people are again supported to consider the key issues in more depth. The next stage in the process involves an **action research phase**. The research question becomes articulated as a research project. This can take a wide range of forms, from the development of a video response, a podcast discussion, journaling or blogging, through to the writing of poetry. These projects are then analysed in the **final phase of interpretation**. The children young people look to interpret their work, their responses and attribute further meaning to these phases of work. At each phase, the children and young people are being empowered to develop their own analysis and critique of the online environment with which they are dealing.

Young people's opinions are frequently seen (or characterised) as simply individual views, and therefore not representative. There is a need to show evidence for their perspectives if they are to have an influence. The WYRED project aims to help young people research the digital issues that matter to them, so that their concerns are backed up with evidence, so that they can have an influence.

Through the application of the WYRED methodology over three cycles and across a wide variety of operational sites, standpoints and international contexts, partners have seized opportunities to triangulate and validate emerging data. This has allowed for the testing of the consistency of findings and the deepening and widening of understanding of the WYRED approach. Through each cycle, partners have been innovative in conceptual framing and developing multi-perspective mapping of children's and young people's exploration of their digital lives.

Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

Unless officially marked PUBLIC, this document and its contents remain the property of the beneficiaries of the WYRED Consortium and may not be distributed or reproduced without the express approval of the Project Coordinator.

WYRED aims to:

- Amplify youth voices.
- Strengthen youth views through youth-led research.
- Connect youth with decision-makers.
- Broaden understanding of the digital society.
- Make youth perspectives matter.

Cycle 1 focused on the testing of this methodology with children and young people across the full partnership. This cycle led to the engagement of over 500 children and young people in a consultative process, leading in turn to 280 of these participating in almost 100 separate projects. An online platform was developed to allow the sharing of these local projects and promote an engagement between the target groups and key policy stakeholders, from education, youth work and community sectors. Cycle 2 allowed for further iterations of the methodological steps. Partners have again reached out to over 500 children and young people in consultative forums, facilitating conversations and discussions regarding perceptions about their online lives. Through these social dialogues, a further set of 58 research questions were elaborated, leading to 50 projects with almost 300 children and young people. Cycle 3 is the focus of this report and during this period, partners worked with over 700 children and young people. Again, some 50 social dialogues led to the articulation of over 160 research questions and projects. During this phase, as well as sharing results through the WYRED platform, children and young people had the opportunity to engage in a series of focused themed fortnights of online activity.

Through these three iterative cycles, participation in the dialogues, projects and presentations allowed for these children and young people to share their qualitative and quantitative research analysis of commonly faced challenges. Partners were focused on an examination of themes and topics of interest to children and young people related to digital society issues. The priority for WYRED projects was to draw out recommendations or conclusions from the children and young people around their chosen research projects and topics of interest. These recommendations and lessons were in turn presented to stakeholders and policymakers.

In order to surface these insights, the children and young people were facilitated to evaluate their own projects through a range of creative methods, informal and dynamic approaches, as well as specifically tailored toolkits. These self-administered processes assisted the children and young people to identify the value and relevance of what they had been doing within WYRED

Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

Unless officially marked PUBLIC, this document and its contents remain the property of the beneficiaries of the WYRED Consortium and may not be distributed or reproduced without the express approval of the Project Coordinator.

activities. This was also a core element of the WYRED approach in ensuring that children and young people would be active in this process through choosing the messages, formats and channels that they regard as most appropriate to present their results, in relation to what it is that they want to explain and how they would present this. Evaluation toolkits were available for partners to implement and tailor in their local environments.

This report is structured in three parts:

- Section 2 presents evaluation results from cycle three, with quantitative and qualitative overviews of key themes and lessons learnt. Examples of emerging best practice cases are highlighted in relation to the steps in the WYRED approach, with a focus on validation and triangulation.
- Section 3 presents a thematic analysis of the body of evidence produced through WYRED projects, with a focus on the six themes of interest in Cycle 3 work.
- Section 4 examines key insights from Cycle 3 in relation to how children's and young people's voices have shaped these understandings of digital society.

2. Overview of Results

2.1 WYRED Activities in Cycle 3

During the third cycle of the project, all partners continued to engage with children and young people in a range of settings and spaces, from the formal environment including primary and second level schools, to training institutes and third level colleges. Informal and non-formal sectors were also selected, including youth services and centres and youth cafes. Within these settings, Cycle 3 also continued the activity base of the earlier cycles, whereby creative projects and actions were undertaken by children and young people in response to a particular question or issue pertaining to their online lives and wider digital society concerns.

The facilitators from each partner continue to employ the WYRED research and evaluation toolkit (including templates and guidelines) to support and guide the process. All partners in turn made use of this toolkit while facilitating research activities. The facilitators have also instigated an active community of practice in Cycle 3, involving online sessions and webinars that allowed for sharing of experiences and co-ordination of new approaches to the design, delivery and review steps within the WYRED cycle.

Within Cycle 3, the WYRED steps continued to begin with the social dialogue space, where themes are examined, with discussion and dialogue taking place in relation to the digital lives of the young participants. The conversations lead to the development of a series of questions that they would like to further address, with the most interesting becoming the focus for research projects and activities. The projects are then undertaken either within groups or individually, with the voice and priorities of the children and young people as the core of the research process. The final stage of their WYRED research involves self-evaluation, reflection and analysis.

Their work does not end with the production of research artefacts. Dissemination and sharing of practice becomes for many the most important stage. The individuals and groups present their work as public projects in the common area in the WYRED platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, García-Holgado, & Seoane-Pardo, 2019), and in the respective online community areas. Participants are always encouraged to read and review projects developed by other children and young people within the platform.

The following diagram explains these four stages of the cycle from both perspective of partner and participant.

Cycle 3 also involved the opportunity to bring their projects into activities associated with Thematic Conversation Fortnights. These fortnights allowed for participants in classroom settings or in youth centres to come together in online spaces either synchronous or asynchronous to share their experiences of WYRED and of their wider digital lives. Participants were supported to compare and contrast their experiences with projects run by peers across participating countries, covering themed topics.

2.2 Overview of Participant Numbers and Activities

Through all phases of the WYRED cycle, the consortium has facilitated a wide range of exploratory research activities, during which groups of children and young people, internationally or locally, have investigated and examined issues that concern them in the digital arena. They have been supported to do this through creative projects (e.g. prototyping solutions following an ideation session to tackle pre-defined challenges) or more conventional research projects. Interaction during the research activities has taken place both on the dedicated platform as well as through other media. Each group that is working on a research activity administers its own space on the platform to record and review work progress.

The initial engagement with the children and young people takes place through an outreach and social dialogue phase. To date, this has involved:

- Cycle 1: 32 Social dialogue sessions with 550 Children and Young People.
- Cycle 2: 76 Social dialogue sessions with 538 Children and Young People.
- Cycle 3: 50 Social dialogue sessions with 657 Children and Young People.

Once engaged, facilitators have worked with the children and young people, using the WYRED Activity Toolkit to assist them in elaborating research questions and projects. Each project in turn generates a series of research artefacts. Over the course of the project cycles, it has led to:

- Cycle 1: 438 active participants involved in generating 101 research projects and associated artefacts.
- Cycle 2: 414 active participants involved in generating 43 research projects and associated artefacts.
- Cycle 3: 721 active participants involved in generating 118 research projects and associated artefacts.

This section presents some further breakdown of these dialogue sessions to illustrate how the children and young people responded to their discussions about digital society and also further analysis of the research activities that were carried out to demonstrate the scope of the learning achieved across the wide range of settings. Feedback from facilitators, participants and stakeholders is included, as well as short case studies where relevant to highlight key points in the delivery and evaluation of the WYRED steps.

2.3 Social Dialogues in Cycle 3

Of the 50 social dialogues held in Cycle 3, almost 70% were held with the same groups of children and young people. The remaining 30% tended to be organised as one off events, usually as a full day workshop. The more typical approach was to work with a group of children and young people over a number of sessions, whereby the WYRED themes could be presented and discussed in some detail, before moving onto the research phases. On average some 13 children and young people participated in each social dialogue. The highest proportion of these participants were aged between 14 and 19 years (45%), with the older cohort of participants aged over 20 making up 38% and the youngest group aged 9 to 13 years at 17%.

Through the social dialogue workshops and sessions, the most common WYRED themes addressed were associated with “Living on social media, living with stress” and “Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy”.

The approach taken by facilitators varied depending on the age profile of the participants and the settings. For example in working with young people in youth centres, one partner described the process:

“In all the sessions we are using non-formal education as a tool to ensure that young people express themselves freely and if they wish to do so. The techniques we are usually using are brainstorming, role-plays, and discussions. In the social dialogues we would start with brainstorming to see what will be the first thoughts of young people that come to their minds when it comes to the topics. Then we would group the comments into more specific topics that seemed similar and split into small groups. In smaller groups, there was one participant in charge of taking care of time and keeping notes as well as ensuring that the discussion doesn’t go into a completely different topic. We were aiming at gathering information and creating draft research questions that young people will further explore in small groups, online or offline”.

In working with a young age group within a primary school setting, the following case study highlights how one of the partner organisation managed their social dialogue phase within a local school.

Social Dialogue in Practice (Early Years Organisation- North of Ireland)

The participants were children from three Primary 6 classes – ages 9-10 years from 2 different schools. Within each school while the children knew each other, they had not worked together in a context like this before. The sessions took place within their classrooms and also within a spare classroom devoted to WYRED project in one of the schools. The facilitators also had access to a computer suite, where they worked alongside the classroom teachers and substitute teachers. This was the first time both facilitators worked with these 2 schools.

A programme of activities was planned to cover the 9 months of activities with these children. The facilitators began with an overview and explanation of the project, using Icebreakers and group activities designed to capture the voice of the child. A group contract was agreed with each set of children to ensure maximum participation and respect for each other’s opinions.

Initially, conversations focused on how the children engage with the online world:

Follow up sessions asked what the children liked and had challenges with about their online lives.

Digital Citizen	
Mobile Phones	7 - Wrong 2 - As long as not caught 1 - I don't know
Visiting unknown website	9 - Depends on sit 1 - Wrong
Forwarding on nasty texts about other pupils	3 - depends 7 - Wrong
Forwarding on chain emails	10 - I don't know
Letting your friends know about a site to help homework	3 - What's the big deal 3 - right 4 - Depend
Uploading photos of friends to Social Net	2 - Not sure if wrong 4 - Depends 3 - Don't know 1 - Right
Always accepting new friends on S.N	3 - Individual choice 2 - Depends 3 - Not sure 1 - Right

The feedback was similar across each of the settings, with children liking gaming, using Skype to talk to friends and relations “far away”, accessing music and programming through Netflix and Youtube. They also focused on the opportunities to make new friends. The discussion and dialogue also examined their fears of the online world. Common answers in this regard focused on cyberbullying, hacking, scary videos, horror movie trailers, stalkers, getting scammed, trolls, passwords, cursing, fake websites, mean messages, hate messages, being reported for no reason, seeing inappropriate things, Fortnite.

The sessions at this stage also introduced the children to the WYRED online platform.

A range of methods were used with the children to encourage meaningful discussion and engagement. These social dialogue sessions were successfully reviewed with the teachers and the children. All participants were ready to move onto the research phases.

A key feature of the social dialogue phase was to allow issues to surface from the participant perspective. Another facilitator explained the importance of this aspect of WYRED.

“We made sure there was a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere from the start. This included a personal welcome and introduction to each participant, ice-breaker activities as appropriate, basic rules for constructive dialogues, comfortable and collaborative layout arrangements, etc. The moderation was purely focused on facilitating a conversation, rather than guiding it”.

These didactic approaches and methods were important to ensure that the children young people felt in control of the process and as they were moving toward the research phase, that their themes and issues were

“Co-working rules were continuously addressed (respect to everyone, every input is important, everyone has the right to speak...). Recordings were done by photographs summarizing the results of the group work in regard to the themes, they were interested in”.

2.4 Research Work in Cycle 3

The vast majority of participants from the social dialogue phase continued their involvement within the WYRED process during each cycle, by taking up the opportunity to carry out research work. In fact in phase 3, there was a multiplier effect noted when extra children and young people became involved in the research work, even in some cases, when not directly active during the social dialogue phase. This is explained through the youth centre settings. Key stakeholders involved in youth groups and youth centres had experience of social dialogue workshops and sessions. Having been briefed and supported on how the research phases were to operate, they brought WYRED back to their local centres and spaces. These young people effectively acted as catalysts and trainers for their peers within their youth centres.

Over 700 children and young people participated in the research phase during Cycle 3, developing 120 research questions across the partnership. These questions led to the development of 118 specific projects¹.

¹ Appendix 1 includes list of all research questions and projects

Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

Unless officially marked PUBLIC, this document and its contents remain the property of the beneficiaries of the WYRED Consortium and may not be distributed or reproduced without the express approval of the Project Coordinator.

Not all research questions were successfully turned into a project, with ten questions not developed into the more applied research phase. Some seven of the research questions were developed into a series of 2 or 3 projects. Facilitators maintained the WYRED approach from the social dialogue phase, whereby the children and young people were provided the forum to explore the WYRED themes and focus in on the particular areas that interested them. In order to define research questions, further sessions and workshops took place. Participants were supported to become more forensic at this stage. The themes required refinement and they were facilitated to ensure that their specific interests became a focus for further research. Within the classrooms, the youth centres and the university campuses, research groups were formed or individuals decided to work alone.

In some instances, the class group worked together to develop a series of interlinked projects. In other instances, a wide range of subjects were explored and research topics and themes outlined. Research processes were then examined. Participants were introduced to quantitative and qualitative techniques. Interviewing skills were introduced. Surveys were designed and datasets produced.

The following case study highlights a typical example of the delivery of the research work phases within WYRED. It illustrates that within a group of children and young people, they find a wide range of research topics to explore, as well as creative means to presenting their research results.

Research Project in Practice (PYE- UK)

As part of a large WYRED project within a school in Barrowford, Manchester, a group of 30 children were facilitated to explore how they are currently interacting with the digital world. They were aged from 9-10 years and were supported by teachers and WYRED facilitators to open up the discussions. They then focused on the WYRED themes as part of their social dialogue phase. Having completed the social dialogue work, the participants decided to focus on themes associated with self-image and its presentation online, Internet safety and privacy as well as issues associated with digital participation. These discussions led to a specific interest in following up on a wide range of research questions of which led to an ever wider range of responses from the children in terms of research activities and interactive projects.

Research Question	Response by the Children
1. Why is Fortnite (computer game) for 12 year olds and over?	Interview
2. What does it mean to be respectful online?	Pamphlet
3. Why do people change their appearance to fit in?	Poem and dance
4. What do 9 and 10 year olds do when they are online?	Interview
5. How do we use technology in class?	Drama/play
6. How can we use the internet and digital tools to express ourselves?	Emoji poster & Animojis
7. What do year 5 kids do online?	Survey poster
8. How can we stay safe when adding people we don't know?	Speech
9. Why do people change their appearance to fit in?	Short Story

The children engaged in a writing exercise in order to start into some expressive work. As they did this, they asked each other questions to deepen these explorations and looked at emerging themes and research ideas. These interactions were recorded as were the dialogues between young people and the performances of their creative writing. As they carried out this work, the young people discovered that in their class, the majority of the group were spending more than 5 hours online a day. This shocked many of the children, leading them to consider "what else could we be doing with our time?" and "what are we missing out on?".

Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

Unless officially marked PUBLIC, this document and its contents remain the property of the beneficiaries of the WYRED Consortium and may not be distributed or reproduced without the express approval of the Project Coordinator.

A further key learning point was social media sites were legally restricted to over 13s. This led them to wonder why they have been allowed to engage on these platforms, but also to ask about why Facebook Junior, or Instagram Junior does not exist. The children created a series of new images to express their interest in emojis, using pre-existing emojis to give them inspiration to create their own. Children felt they had more freedom when drawing but that the list of emojis gave them ideas to recognize how they felt based on the pictures.

The following section gives more detail on some of the 9 projects that were undertaken over a series of workshops and facilitated sessions.

Project 1 examined the nature of the online game Fortnite and how the class had experienced it. 6 of the class interviewed their peers about how some key concerns. They devised a series of questions and conducted interviews. A summary of the aggregate results was put together:

Do you think that Fortnite is violent?	No, but the concepts are.
Do you think messages should be taken out?	No, because you wouldn't be able to talk to your friends.
Do you think people should be able to friend you?	Yes, but you should have a way to identify them to stay safe.
In certain types of in-game features (Solo squad or duo), do you find people can be rude with their body language?	There should be a way you can go into duo and not have to talk to people. The mute function can also be used

The children felt that their research could possibly be used to assist the game developers to take their concerns into account. They were unsure as to how to send their research to the game developers.

Project 2 involved 2 students and they decided to develop a pamphlet on how to be respectful when they are online. Project 3 involved 3 students focusing on why people change their appearance to fit in. They were concerned with issues of self-image and how the online world can impact on children's perceptions of themselves. Through this exploration of body image and how people use social media to change their appearance, the children independently came to the conclusion that "it's not needed and we are all beautiful in our own way." The children

worked on an artistic response and produced the following poem to express their feelings about this topic.

Project 4 involved 4 students carrying out a survey of the class in order to discover the range of platforms that are used by their classmates, as well as investigating how long they spend online and some insights into phone use by their parents. The interview delved deeper into how two classmates are using the internet, what games they are playing, social media and age appropriateness.

Project 5 examined how technology is used in the classroom. 5 students came together to put together a drama and role play. This format allowed them to discuss the types of technology that are used in school and how that impacts learning. Their analysis highlighted how teachers use YouTube videos to deliver mindfulness exercises or warm up activities. They also reviewed the range of subject-specific programmes that are designed for classrooms. The conclusions of their research piece were linked to promoting more access to “people sharing skills”, as well as other knowledge or activities that adds to the learning. They also pointed to some challenges

linked to the technology associated with how it sometimes freezes or fails to work at all and this is considered as wasting time for everyone.

For Project 6, 3 students invited the class to draw an emoji of how they were feeling at that moment. They asked whether it is easier to draw an emoji or use the premade ones on a phone. Some said drawing gave them more freedom to be exact. Some said having the preexisting emojis gave them an image which enabled them to express their emotion and be more specific. For their project, the group made a poster of the emojis as drawn by their classmates.

They discovered during their research that some 200 new emojis had been recently added to a typical smartphone, signifying that there is an ongoing extension of these ideas. They explored the new “animoji” feature on the iPhone XR and recorded some insights from their classmates, specifically how this feature “lets you see some of the facial expressions which is better than text or voice notes but not as revealing as a video message.”

Project 7 was linked to the emoji project, whereby 4 students carried out a survey for the emoji group. They produced a poster to represent the survey results. Project 8 was carried out by one student, entitled “How do you stay safe online?” She produced a short video where she highlighted how some key messages and instructions associated with online safety including: “You should talk to people and tell them if strangers contact you. What people might do online that could be unsafe. What you could do to stay safe. How to block or report people.”

Project 9 was developed by two students in relation to why people would feel the need to change their appearance to fit in when developing an online identity. These students researched this topic with their classmates and produced a short story to represent the ideas that surfaced.

Each of the groups involved in these 9 projects presented their results to the classroom and other students in the school, with the support of the facilitator and teachers. This allowed them to feel an achievement about their work and outputs. The positive experiences were acknowledged by the full group and teachers were invited to bring the WYRED methodology into future curricular experiences.

During the evaluation phase, the facilitator and teachers reviewed the process with the students and from the adult perspective, there was a degree of surprise expressed that the children had not realised the extent of the time that they were spending online.

Other important developments that occurred during the research project phase related to the manner in which the children had investigated their experiences of being online and feeling safe. Two key findings from this research highlighted that:

1. While online, more than half of the class had experienced unwanted strangers in their online space.
2. Furthermore, more than half the class had left online space because they did not feel safe. There were experiences and clear articulation of grooming, of catfish and of adult strangers posing as children their age.

Projects in Cycle 3 continued the trends of innovative analysis and presentation of results. Many young people identified the key themes and issues that face them as linked to a lack of economic security, online bullying and precarious living situations (online and offline). Other WYRED themes were explored linked to how they can access reliable information and how they experience education as members of ethnic minorities. One group of WYRED participants worked to develop of a poetry magazine that was published and presented to their peers within their youth centre. They introduced the publication with the following:

“We all identify as working class, or from a working class background. We have complicated families, and many of us have caring responsibilities at home. Some of us are Muslim, some of us are Christian, some of us are atheist and some of us are spiritual. We have many different skills and interests including spoken word, music, drama, art, sports, technology and social media We are responsible, humble, passionate and open minded”.

When evaluating their experiences of WYRED, these young people highlighted the empowering nature of their research and expression. Conducting the project had given them a clear focus, as well as “strength and clarity, once they realised they had a voice”.

2.5 Interpretation and Analysis in Cycle 3

Throughout the evaluation and interpretation phase, the children and young people maintained their involvement. As participants, they were given control over the research process. They were also supported to interpret their findings and find the most appropriate means of presenting their results. Projects were in turn presented to peers, parents, teachers, youth and community workers, local and national politicians, as well as other stakeholders from policy arenas. The sphere of influence of projects in each country was vast, with school and youth centre policies being altered as a result of the research work, new groups established to take on research findings within universities, new modules being added to teacher training courses, WYRED being added to school curricula and college induction courses. MEPs were lobbied and engaged within research cycles and other WYRED activities. Datasets and research instruments were shared across countries and settings.

As well as the ongoing presentation of research results, all partners conducted evaluation exercises within their varied WYRED settings. The facilitators employed a range of approaches and methods as appropriate. For some facilitators, a series of interviews were conducted:

“The Principals and teachers within the schools were very positive about the WYRED project and the methodology introduced to the children was a very effective tool to capture their views and opinions. We interviewed stakeholders after the Showcase event and filmed interviews with 5 stakeholders”.

In working with the younger age groups, the children and young people were asked to indicate “One positive thing from being involved in the WYRED Project” and “What could we do better?” A sample of feedback from some children is presented below:

Positive Experiences: “We got to do some Skypes with Turkey”; “We learnt about the dangers of the internet”; “We can use technology safely”; “We learnt how to create questionnaires and analyse them”; “Self-image is more important to some people than others and more important online.” “We all worked together to find consent and permission information.” “Our group has learnt to work together” “WYRED has taught us how to stay safe online.” “Fake news causes harm”; “I liked working in a group”.

Verbal feedback was collected through a range of methods, including tools such as target evaluations, “circle time” and collection of Post it notes on flipchart.

Facilitators also addressed the following 7 questions with their stakeholders, including principals, teachers, youth workers and others acting as gatekeepers in the formal and informal sectors, where WYRED has been applied.

1. Did participants perceive the WYRED project as inclusive?
2. Were the themes relevant?
3. Was understanding clarified through social dialogue process?
4. Did the social dialogue process allow voice to be heard?
5. Were participants satisfied with participation in process?
6. Were they satisfied with research activities as process?
7. Were they satisfied with research activities as outputs?

The results of this evaluation work were overwhelmingly positive. Over 80% of respondents answered 5 of the 7 questions in the positive. The key challenges tended to be associated with the time commitment involved in order to be able to deliver the WYRED process in full. The school or youth centre was often unable to manage the extra support requested or sometimes required by a child or young person, who was aiming to carry out extra work on their project.

In some instances, the projects completed were of such a high standard that they were entered into national competitions and student fairs, where some projects received awards from a scientific jury. In other cases, projects were presented by the students as part of youth delegations to national and European parliaments.

Feedback from stakeholders in Turkey indicated:

“We believe that two main lessons can be learned from our experience with the WYRED project. The first lesson is that if we aim to give freedom to children and young people, space and support to work on ideas, we need to accept that sometimes they may want to take the projects in a different direction than we expected. This allows them to fully apply their creativity and ingenuity, supported by their passion. If we were to enforce a specific direction, even within WYRED, we would fall short of the very principles of WYRED, i.e. that children and young people can achieve great things for society if given the freedom and support to develop their potential. We believe that the number and the quality of the projects produced support the above statement”.

3. Analysis of WYRED Research Themes

Through all three cycles of the WYRED project, the consortium has facilitated a wide range of exploratory research activities (158 social dialogues and 262 research projects), during which over 1700 children and young people, internationally or locally, have investigated and examined issues that concern them in the digital arena. They have been supported to do this through creative projects (e.g. prototyping solutions following an ideation session to tackle pre-defined challenges) or more conventional research projects.

Interaction during the research activities has taken place both on the dedicated platform as well as through other media. Each group that is working on a research activity administers its own space on the platform to record and review work progress. Participants have also made use of the platform to engage in transnational discussions and debates both asynchronously and synchronously.

Through the initial cycles of the WYRED project, the children and young people were the key drivers of the thematic focus. Their voice was facilitated to articulate the direction of their research interests. The focus of the research activities has been consistently trained on the lens of the digital society and how they are relating to its reach in their lives.

The main themes that were of interest to the children and young people have been grouped accordingly across each cycle. Emerging from the first cycle of activities, the children and young people had identified the following 11 themes and discussion points as important interests.

Cycle 1 Themes	
Internet & Security	Bullying
Internet & Social Media	Politics
Digital society/ world	Employment
Environment pollution	Culture and identity
Education	Wellbeing & Health
Self-image	

The children and young people were supported and facilitated to train their lens in a more targeted manner, allowing for the more specific themes to emerge. As the WYRED methodology was implemented again through the second cycle, facilitators encouraged the young people to explore a range of themes that were more and more connected to their digital lives.

Cycle 2 Themes	
Self-image and its presentation online	Media literacy
Gender discrimination, and gender differences online	Impact of hyper-connectivity and IoE on the individual
Stereotyping in online contexts	Digital activism
Internet safety	Future of employment in a digital world
Internet privacy	Changes in education in a digital world
Cyber security	Tolerance of different cultures, and integration of migrants
Living on social media	Living with stress online
Access to reliable information, and fake news	Digital divide
New technologies and their impacts on different field in the future	Cyberbullying and online abuse

Through this iterative process of again evaluating all research activities, these themes have again been reviewed through the Cycle 3 research process. Through Cycle 3, all research activities were focused clearly on the following agreed digital society themes, as they had emerged through Cycles 1 and 2, as well as through the Delphi processes.

Each partner collected and collated detailed data on the projects being conducted and their focus through Cycle 3. Accordingly, we can present the thematic breakdown of projects as undertaken during the third cycle.

Cycle 3 Theme	Number of Projects	Proportion of Projects
1. Self-image and its presentation online	22	19%
2. Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping	26	22%
3. Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security	16	14%
4. Living on social media, living with stress	19	16%
5. Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy	12	10%
6. Digital participation and activism, digital divide	23	19%
	118	100%

The thematic area that attracted the most interest from WYRED participants was the area of gender and stereotyping. This was especially the case with older participants within universities. Over one in five projects were developed with a focus on gender. One in ten projects were developed to explore the area of “fake news” and reliable information. This tended to attract a

younger age profile, with the primary and second level school students more inclined to research this area.

In looking at the numbers of participants who selected particular themes, the same trend is clear, with gender and digital activism as the two most popular themes.

Cycle 3 Theme	Number of Participants	Proportion of Participants
1. Self-image and its presentation online	94	13%
2. Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping	166	23%
3. Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security	121	17%
4. Living on social media, living with stress	107	15%
5. Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy	102	14%
6. Digital participation and activism, digital divide	131	18%
	721	100%

This section now seeks to examine the nature and scope of projects conducted under each of these themes. Through looking at a examples of thematic projects, the methodological approaches are better understood as are the opportunities for the children and young people to undertake research regarding their positions within a digital world. Some insights are presented as to the types of conclusions and recommendations that the children and young people are pointing to, based on their research activity.

3.1 Self-image and its presentation online

Some 22 projects were carried out by 94 participants on the theme of self-image and how its presentation online affects children and young people.

A project carried out by a group of 6 students aged 17 years focused on the questions “How do YP manage self-image in online contexts? Are YP approaches to management of self-image online different from older generations?” The WYRED process was facilitated face to face, using online tools to assist the research. The young people used mobile phones to produce video recordings of their reflections and interviews on this theme. As well as discussing this subject area with their peers, they also interview adults to gauge their opinions.

As the group were used to working together and collaborating on artistic projects, they fully embraced the WYRED approach, even if they acknowledge that the research work “was new to all and many found it challenging”. This group focused on the differences between their management of self- image as individuals, compared to how older generations use social media tools and platforms. According to the facilitator, the key insight “was the degree of investment, while all use social media and present themselves to some degree, the older generations are less concerned by the difficulties involved. The conclusions focused on the need for resilience and self-respect, which are communicated well in the reflection video they made.”

This becomes a common conclusion and finding from many of the projects in this area. Specifically that children and young people require a strong degree of resilience to be able to cope with and manage their online lives. Other projects asked questions about why young people change personalities when online or how do we protect ourselves. Research conclusions tended to point to the importance of being supported, self-aware and possessing resilience. Recommendations tended to request that schools and youth work settings would work to educate young people in relation to how to promote and build capacities and competences associated with digital resilience.

3.2 Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping

Of the 26 projects that focused on gender related online issues and themes, all were carried out by young people aged 17 years or older. For some, they chose to conduct an academic research project examining whether patriarchal structures can be found with social media structures and systems. These students produced posters that were presented to their peers and their tutors. These were instrumental in creating further debate and discourse within their campus. Others examined the relationship between sport, marketing and social media stereotypes. Again, these results were presented in order to stimulate and continue discussion amongst the student group. These projects were also shared within the WYRED platform and were circulated through the online discussion forums during Cycle 3.

A project carried out by a group of asked the question whether the online world is increasing gender discrimination. Their conclusions and recommendations were again widely shared:

“We can clearly see that the online world is increasing gender discrimination, especially towards women. These new platforms give new spaces for attackers to cause harm, insult, bully, ... Gender inequality was always present and the online world reflects in a sense what is really happening or going through the minds of some people around the globe. It is a pure reflection of the real situation we’re living every day. More cyber security should be installed in order to protect women from being harassed, stalked, bullied or anything that can harm them, like we do in the offline world. A tool is a tool and a weapon is a weapon, online gender discrimination should be legitimised and erased to stop other young people (men) from being inspired. All of these can only be done with an increase in security and control on what is posted online and who has access to it”.

As well as pointing to the importance of challenging bullying behaviour, these young people also point to the importance of targeted legislation to prevent harming of women and promote protections.

3.3 Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security

Some 16 projects were carried out by 121 children and young people on the themes of Internet safety and privacy. Apart from one group of 10 year old children, the majority of participants who researched this theme tended to be students at second level formal education or higher.

A project that took place in Austria took a focus on the development of an “Anti-(Cyber)Bullying Strategy for the Centre of Inclusive Schools”. A group of 18 young people aged between 13 and

14 years developed a research question “How can the Internet get safer for my daily use? What has to be considered, to be safe in the internet?” and “What can be done against bullying in the Internet and in School? “Of the group of young people from different classes, many of the students were dealing with cognitive or emotional difficulties. In each session one to two teachers supported the facilitator.

As a result, the young people were fully engaged over this series of workshops and sessions, involving their teachers and other stakeholders from within the school. As well as building capacity of the students through the research activities, the buy in from the school was also achieved through the WYRED steps. The inclusive nature of the project ensured that all participants were involved and could feel that their voice was heard, especially through the thematic development work.

The (Cyber) bullying project was the final result of the dialogues and research sessions. Through clarification and further iteration of the research work with the young people and involving the school personnel, the research output became more targeted at the school policies. The culmination of the project work was the production of a dedicated anti-cyber bullying policy for the school that was presented to the school principal at a dedicated event. According to the facilitator, “before the presentation of the strategy all participants worked on it and proudly presented their strategy to the headmaster. They argue that the strategy is not only relevant for themselves but also for all their colleagues and the teachers in school”.

In this instance, we again see the power of both the educate and legislate joint approach. Through engaging the educators and developing a policy level response within the school environment, a sustainable outcome is achieved. The students are informed and aware about the causes and effects of cyber bullying and the school community have a consistent policy framework to deal with any cases of bullying as they may happen.

3.4 Living on social media, living with stress

Some 107 children and young people took part in 19 research projects on the theme of social media and the impact on stress.

Much of the research under this theme focused on the examining whether social media can have a positive impact on mental health, particularly examining the role that online peer support communities can play in supporting people in need. In such instances, the research pointed to positive roles for social media.

Conversely, research also looked at the nature of “digital addiction”, as experienced by young people in Israel. Research was conducted with peer groups within youth centres and youth groups. Some implications of digital addiction were considered to involve:

- Damage to social relations through a lack of personal contacts and face to face interaction.
- Physical damage through, for example, to damage to eyes and joints.
- Waste of time, taking people away from more meaningful social activities including activism.

All students said they are "living in their smartphones" a lot of time every day. Most of them would like to occupy themselves less with their screens. There was a discussion about "screen time": there was a disagreement about the typical time devoted to screens, but most agree that it is hours per day. Some students are busy with their screens four hours a day, maybe even more.

Regarding imposed restrictions, there were different opinions. Some of the students said that enforced restrictions and prohibitions are not effective. On the contrary, they achieve the opposite result, as young people will continue to do the prohibited things. It was mentioned that what matters is not necessarily the time spent on "living in the screen", but rather the manner in which the "addiction" is expressed, namely how the user copes when he or she needs to log out. The crux of the problem is the difficulty of disconnecting, even though you know it would have been better to do something else. Some of the participants noted that they are aware that their "screen time" is exaggerated and comes at the expense of something else they would like to do, but the problem is that it is very hard to disconnect. Students often cancel things in order to "be on screen" - for example, they sacrifice sleeping or watching TV.

The research group decided to examine a series of possible future scenarios and asked participants to express their opinion on the likely situation 10 years from now. To this end, the following alternative scenarios were proposed for the year 2029:

- (1) The situation is grave. Most people are digitally-addicted. Many are hospitalized or suffer greatly because there is no proper treatment.
- (2) The problem has disappeared. Thanks to education and public campaigns, people have learned to find the right balance in their digital activity.
- (3) There is no problem at all, because the digital activity is perceived as the new normal, a "natural" condition, and is no longer considered an addiction.

The majority of respondents considered that the position would become worse. But their recommendation was for the second option to be a policy aspiration. With this in mind, they promoted a more overarching education policy that would address the potential impacts of digital addiction. They also recommend that the voice of young people is included when such a policy is being developed and reviewed.

These findings and recommendations were shared through the WYRED platform and became a focus for online conversations associated with the theme of online lives and how young people are constructing their own solutions.

3.5 Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy

Some 12 projects were carried out by 102 children and young people under the theme of fake news and reliable information.

In developing research projects in relation to this theme, many children and young people became fascinated about the propagation of fake news and the industrial structures that promote the development of such stories. They decided to carry out research with their peers in school communities and within their youth centres to examine the extent to which people are “fooled” by these stories.

Their conclusions focused on the challenges associated with distinguishing between real and false information on the Internet. Some participants noted that in many cases the problem is not necessarily false information but information that is only partially true, or biased. Some students think they have the ability to distinguish between true and false info, and some of them say they do not have such ability. Some feel that their ability is only limited to subjects known to them thanks to personal experience. One participant said that in his opinion, this is the only way to distinguish - even though not everyone can personally experience everything.

The implication is that one should rely on the knowledge and personal experience of others. Some participants noted that the problem also exists in non-digital media and it is not advisable to rely on journalists. They believe that most information in the media (any type of media) is either biased or only partially true.

For a younger cohort of researchers, they similarly concluded though their research project that:

“Not everything that is in the news is true and sometimes it is very hard to tell the difference between what is real news and what is fake news! Our research tells us that people think they can spot fake news most of the time, when in fact they cannot! People should be careful about what they believe- If it seems too good to be true, or silly, it’s probably not true! There should be stricter rules for people who make the news and for magazines, newspapers and the Internet, so that people are not fooled by fake news

reports. If you're not sure if a news report is real or fake, check out other sources to see if you can find out more".

The recommendations again are suggesting that tighter regulation and focus on media channels is necessary to ensure that there can be a higher degree of trust when approaching online sources of news.

3.6 Digital participation and activism, digital divide

Some 131 children and young people took part in 23 WYRED projects on the theme of digital participation.

A wide range of research activities were undertaken, including a case study of 'Better neighbourhood' projects as an example of how e-democracy platform can promote civic engagement.

Such research interests also examined how education is to be used to promote a more inclusive "online society". The following conclusion was the result of a collective project by third level students in Belgium:

"Educating towards an active and democratic citizenship should not be reduced to just "civic education", especially if understood as a mere knowledge of the institutions, their relationships and the mechanisms of civil coexistence, rather it should be configured as a path that educates the values and attitudes of an individual and social ethic together. Communication and information technologies have improved the real possibility of participation of individual citizens. This translates into a concrete opportunity to exercise one's right of citizenship: through participation in consultations; through the evaluation and the influence exercised on the work of the directors; through immediate access to data, documents and information. The consolidation of the digital dimension as a "real space" for the exercise of active citizenship is linked to the familiarity that the individual matures with the use of tools, applications and services that allow the possibility of actively and effectively intervening in local, national and European decision-making processes. This, of course, must be accompanied by a "digital transparency" project implemented by public authorities".

The promotion of active citizenship models for policymakers therefore requires an urgent "reboot" to take account of the reality of online lives of young people.

Research projects also looked at the state of play of digital activism within their peer groups:

“Digital activism has proven to be quite successful in the last decade. Decision makers use the internet as much as we do and if something is shared enough it will captivate their attention and maybe even influence their decisions. We can see how through social media and advocating for climate change, decision makers around the world have taken note, heard young people’s concerns and started to make some changes bit by bit, not the point we’d like them to but it’s a start. Of course, the world will not be changed through a Facebook post and most of them will only raise awareness, but if enough people agree on the same idea and the heads of state see/hear that voice, it increases the chances of making a change. We should not only be active on social media though, changes are also made every day with small actions”.

Taking this further, another project saw that there is potential for social media as a tool for activists and that some decision-makers are aware of comments and hashtags. However, as mentioned above, the importance of face to face engagement and the use of other strategies is equally important. In this regard, the project highlights the importance of WYRED as a complimentary approach for activists:

“You might not always be successful, but if you comment, share and debate enough on the platform, the person you’re addressing yourself to will see your ideas and hopefully be inspired by them. WYRED gives you different opportunities and spaces. Allowing you to give detailed information and long developments contrary to what Twitter has to offer”.

The importance of having a shared space for children and young people where they can share ideas and strategies for social change is noted by these research results. Social media channels are clearly not ideal in this regard and while WYRED is a new space for many of the young people, it does offer opportunities for developing more detailed and structured responses to often complicated issues in their lives.

4. Conclusions and Insights

4.1 Children and Young People in Control

The WYRED project has provided a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society. If these children and young people are to play a role in this digital society as drivers of new behaviours and understandings, their voices need to be facilitated and heard. The amplification of this voice requires the creation of a space where the children and young people can come together, initially in local settings supported by trusted facilitators before they can move into an online space. WYRED has allowed this process to happen using a methodology that uses research as the tool or the hook for engagement.

The children and young people are told from the outset that they are in control of the process, their ideas and thoughts are driving the projects. It is based on the principle that young people of all ages have the right to participation and engagement. It has a strong focus on inclusion, diversity and the empowerment of the marginalised. The aim is to replace the disempowering scrutiny of conventional research processes with the empowerment of self-scrutiny and self-organisation through social dialogue and participatory research.

WYRED created a platform from which these children and young people can communicate their perspectives to each other and to other stakeholders. Over the course of the three research Cycles, almost 2000 children and young people have involved themselves in networking activities, international dialogues, participatory research and interpretation phases centred around and driven by themselves, out of which a diverse range of outputs, critical perspectives and other insights have emerged and been shared extensively.

WYRED has focused on tailoring a means by which these children and young people as an emergent and distinct social group can increase their empowerment levels through the making use of a research methodology that is integrally linked to their real digital lives. They have been empowered to ask important questions using the WYRED research steps and come up with their own answers, recommendations and proposals for ensuring that their voice is heard and included in policy responses.

This report has demonstrated how their recommendations have been acted on, their research conclusions acting as catalysts for change and their research activities as triggers for new ideas and for greater levels of engagement in their schools and centres. Children and young people

have indicated that they feel more informed and more confident as a result of their engagement with WYRED. They have expressed that they have a clearer understanding as to the key role they have to play in the digital society, as drivers of change. They consistently noted that decision-makers must take account of their voice in relation to the formation of digital policies.

4.2 WYRED Methodology as Empowerment

The documentation of the research activities through the previous sections of the report (and in more detail on the WYRED platform) present clarity on how the WYRED methods and approaches were applied across a wide range of different age groups, within formal and informal spaces and educational settings and with larger and smaller groups. In many instances, the application of the methodology by a particular facilitator led to significant one-to-one supports being provided. The focus on empowerment and inclusion were key principles throughout the partnership. The application of these principles ensured that there was significant buy in from the partner organisations.

Children and young people were brought together in schools, colleges, youth centres and facilities in over 20 countries across the three WYRED cycles of activity. Facilitators, teachers and youth workers used the social dialogue phase of the process to explain and outline the thematic structures of the project, encouraging the participants to develop research interests and questions within these parameters, ensuring that it was their own particular interests that would come to drive their further engagement. With the next steps, the children and young people were now motivated and inspired to take active control over the process. Their facilitators became back seat passengers in this moving vehicle. Through this process of taking charge of their learning and shaping the questions that they wanted to research, the children and young people became their own agents of change.

The phases of research definition and implementation took a wide range of shapes and turns. Podcasts were developed, poetry magazines were produced, photography exhibits were put together, models were built, site visits were made to NGOs and others with expertise to offer, questionnaires were developed, interviews were carried out with academics, activists and artists. Through it all, the children and young people were in the driving seat. When they needed some support in addressing their research question or unpacking a difficult hypothesis, they would first ask each other and then if required, the WYRED facilitator would step in.

It is clear that from the experience of being active participants within this research process that the children and young people were allowed to develop their own voice, ask their own questions and formulate their own responses. They progressed an agenda that was set by them.

The range of research interests was extremely impressive. As the volume of research artefacts and outputs increased over the course of the three cycles, it became clear that the research findings and conclusions were becoming more and more meaningful. From the big themes associated with online activism and democracy, cyberbullying, stereotyping and homophobia, they were motivated to direct their work and make arguments, conclusions and recommendations that were shared and disseminated across a wide range of forums. When their interest was linked more locally or specifically to themes regarding social media representations and impacts of influencers, they were equally able to articulate sophisticated research questions that led to important insights that could be shared widely.

The children and young people continued to find new ways to present their findings, using online and offline techniques and platforms. They involved their peers. Their school principals, teachers and youth workers were key targets. Where they could, they reached out to policy-makers and decision-makers. Family members were invited to dissemination activities. Competitions were entered, scientific juries made awards and commendations.

Schools and colleges made changes to policies and procedures as a result of WYRED projects. Young people travelled to events across Europe, in which they were invited to present recommendations or participate in high level committees. Some of these events were attended by European Commission representatives, politicians within the House of Lords, delegates from national policy conferences and networking forums. The children and young people were facilitated to see that their action research should have an intended outcome. For many of the WYRED projects, these outcomes were met.

4.3 Completing a Body of Work

The potential for the sharing of results increased as WYRED evolved. Initially the WYRED platform became the main focus that allowed for children and young people to share their projects, their experiences and thoughts. They could make use of specific conversation threads and thematic areas to drive their discussions. The platform also acted as the repository and archive of the 262 individual and group projects, their resulting artefacts, outputs and stories.

Each separate presentation, spreadsheet, research report, video or podcast has been shared within an international community of children and young people.

Through Cycle 3, opportunities for greater online engagement were promoted and taken up by children and young people from across the partner countries and centre. Through a series of structured online conversations, build over a fortnight at a time, classrooms came together synchronously across Europe to share their work and their conclusions. These were videoed and shared for further discussion. Students and academics made use of these fortnights to examine research approaches and tools, often through asynchronous discussion threads. Ongoing conversations continue to be facilitated through the platform. The success of these engagements is linked to the fact that the children and young people are setting their agenda.

Two trends became visible during the final cycle as the body of WYRED work was increasing.

Greater involvement in online activities: through Cycle 3, as a greater volume of research was being produced, the children and young people became keener to share their results and make use of the spaces being provided. As more opportunities were created for the sharing and using of different online spaces (Online Conversation Fortnights, Online Festival, etc.) children and young people became more active users.

Evidence of triangulation within the data sources and research outputs being produced: as the volume of projects were structured by facilitators and analysed by the WYRED team in relation to the 6 key digital themes, common conclusions were being reached again and again using different methods and employing different presentation and validation techniques. Qualitative interviews and podcasts were focusing on comparable recommendations on the same topics as results from in depth focus group work, quantitative surveys and desk research.

4.4 Educate and Legislate

These trends in relation to more convergent and connected findings, together with demand for greater online engagement give the project a greater weight as the next steps for the WYRED Association are planned. The key recommendations from these collective activities are pointing towards the critical importance of ensuring that the voice of children and young people is central in future developments in their digital society. Within this perspective, the central insights, across the consortium coalesce under two headings: “educate” and “legislate”.

Across each theme, the children and young people asked questions and developed responses about how their digital lives are being affected by ever evolving landscapes, where their

experience of growing up and maturing has been in many ways mediated by technological developments and experiments. Whether they are examining the nature of digital addiction, online bullying and clicktivism, each time their answer is that there is a need for increased education, supported by legislative responses putting the wellbeing of the child and young person ahead of corporate interests. In each thematic area, these common insights prevail.

While WYRED research projects into the attitudes and perspectives of young people tend to demonstrate that the majority feel relatively optimistic about their own future, they consistently highlight better access to educational opportunities as critical factors in their digital lives. This does not simply mean more formal education. From the research activities and results, they are pointing to a more responsive and targeted education approach that takes the voice of the child and young person seriously. For example, when there are debates regarding online safety and privacy, a typical response of a more formal approach to “teaching” children and young people the “right responses” is not regarded as effective.

The second key insight is linked to the desire for a legislative response from the adult world. Many of the research outputs and online conversations have highlighted an almost pervasive lack of faith in institutions and in politics. The children and young people are extremely concerned about their environment and democratic structures. However, they do not regard themselves as “radicals” when they are posing questions regarding our “grown-up” responses to the many existential threats that they are highlighting. The WYRED projects have highlighted how these young people can shape and direct their online interactions, thereby appearing to enhance their autonomy and personal agency.

So when these children and young people are pointing to solutions and fixes, they are already aware of the complexity of the worlds of the decision-makers and policy-makers. However, they can see clearly that there is a requirement for a legislative “fix” in so many of the thematic areas that they have studied and researched. For instance, when online bullying or fake news or racist abuse remains pervasive through each of the new platforms that they visit and make use of, they are clear as to who should be held to account. They consistently point to the need for the proper regulation of the platform and their corporate interests.

These two insights emerge and become evident throughout the WYRED body of evidence on the platform, through the reporting, through the online conversations and discussion.

The children and young people consistently display a sophisticated analysis of their digital lives. They are managing a balancing act between public and private narratives, positive and negative self-image and these interplays. They are examining potential correlations between rates of depression amongst teenagers and time spent on social media. They are also demonstrating the pleasure and stimulation to be found on screens and smartphones that unleash positive and creative urges.

Through their engagement within the WYRED methodology, they are exploring their potential in a myriad of new and exciting ways. They are part of their analysis, situated as they are in an ever moving tide with unlimited availability of social media outlets for viewing, content-creating, and editing. Under such constant exposure, social comparison and an on-demand culture, they are also developing new ways of being parts of groups and social networks.

So when these same children and young people bring their sophisticated analysis and recommendations to the dual edges of education and legislation, we must recognise that they are reaching these conclusions as members of a more digitally oriented social environment and as part of the WYRED process, whose critical analysis is framed in relation to themes of inclusion and equality.

The children and young people have examined their “technology-rich culture” and have clearly stated that we need to review and re-examine whether this is working to inspire their skills and interests in relation to their formal and informal education experiences, in relation to better understanding mental health issues or social media impacts. From the perspective of WYRED participants, the response of education is not currently delivering. It is not embracing the voice of the child and young person.

Through WYRED project developments and responses, children and young people are also articulating questions that they want to answer about how their online lives are being governed. They are highlighting a lack of concern or humanity, pointing to structures that are promoting unhappiness, anxiety and lack of control. They are asking in this regard for a commitment to legislate for their wellbeing.

Appendix 1: Research Questions Developed in Cycle 3

1.	What are the effects on YP of online LGBT+ discrimination?
2.	How does online gender discrimination affect mental health?
3.	How do YP manage self-image in online contexts?
4.	Are YP approaches to management of self-image online different from older generations?
5.	What are the risks for minority YP of engaging in online digital activism?
6.	What are the effects on YP of colourism online?
7.	How do banter and memes affect YP online?
8.	How do you use technology in your daily life? Which apps do you use to talk with your friends?
9.	How do you use technology in your daily life? Which apps do you use to talk with your friends?
10.	Do you buy your things in online shops?
11.	Have you observed how adults around you use the apps?
12.	Who is watching us and how are we watching each other?
13.	What are these terms and conditions that we agree to everyday?
14.	Do you know which is a stereotype?
15.	Stereotypes are true when they start to play?
16.	Do you think that people from different cultures perceive stereotypes in the same way than you?
17.	Are there stereotypes on the internet?
18.	How can we be more active participants within our democracies?
19.	Are you doing something in order to reach this point that you and/or society deem "perfect"?
20.	What conscious or even unconscious impact do you think this idea of the "perfect" person has on people?
21.	Have you observed how adults around you use the apps?
22.	How did migration in our country affect air pollution, water pollution etc. and what can we do about that?
23.	How did migration of refugees change the population?
24.	What are the challenges of technology for disabled people?
25.	Where is the place of technology?
26.	What is the impact of technology on academic success?
27.	What kind of career are you planning by taking future jobs in hand?
28.	Do children really read and understand consent before going online?
29.	Does Cyberbullying happen more often than bullying in real life?
30.	Is hacking illegal?
31.	Can people tell the difference between real and fake news?
32.	Is self-image more important online than in the real world?
33.	How can the Internet get safer for my daily use? What has to be considered, to be safe in the internet?
34.	What can be done against bullying in the Internet and in School?
35.	How can fake news be distinguished from real news?

36.	What are criteria for buying a computer?
37.	How can we build a one-meter tall Robot?
38.	Why is Fortnite for 12 year olds and over?
39.	What does it mean to be respectful online?
40.	Why do people change their appearance to fit in?
41.	What do 9 and 10 year olds do when they are online?
42.	How do we use technology in class?
43.	How can we use the internet and digital tools to express ourselves?
44.	What do year 5 kids do online?
45.	How can we stay safe when adding people we don't know?
46.	Why do people change their appearance to fit in?
47.	What is digital activism? How can we get involved?
48.	How do we become more educated to get reliable information?
49.	How can we make more positive self images on social media
50.	How much are we being followed in our lives and on social media?
51.	Who invented Tik Tok, snapchat, skype, twitter, sky?
52.	How do we deal with bad behaviour online
53.	What comes after facial recognition?
54.	What should you do if you get banned or hacked?
55.	How do deal with digital addiction? Are there technological solutions?
56.	How to deal with fake news? How will this issue look in the future? (likely scenarios)
57.	How to deal with privacy on the web? How will this issue look in the future? (likely scenarios)
58.	Does social networks promote the stereotypes?
59.	Does teaching-learning processes an impact in the stereotypes?
60.	How do young people deal with pressure about self-image?
61.	Does Internet influence in sports?
62.	Does social media support the gender gap?
63.	Do stereotypes have an impact in the current society?
64.	Do stereotypes only related to gender or there are stereotypes related to sexual orientation?
65.	Are there gender stereotypes during childhood?
66.	Can Instagram promote a positive perception of the body?
67.	Treating BDD over the internet: is it possible?
68.	How can the educational system tackle gender inequality?
69.	Women and entrepreneurship. What measures to unlock their potential?
70.	Can cyberbullying be stopped by involving young pupils in the fight against it?
71.	Can social Media provide Mental Health Support?
72.	Excessive use of internet and anxiety: a possible correlation?
73.	Can media literacy improve civic engagement?
74.	Learn media literacy through Gamification: a feasible solution?
75.	Can digital tools make democracy more representative?
76.	Can social media be blamed for the rise in narcissism?
77.	Is online self-presentation correlated with self-esteem? A psychological perspective

78.	Gender stereotypes: fixed or inherited?
79.	Gender and Disney princesses: good role models?
80.	Is it possible to prevent the spread of harmful behavior towards teenagers on the Internet?
81.	How do cybersecurity measures protect users and the system?
82.	How does personality change in the world of influencer marketing?
83.	Does the use of social media create stress?
84.	Online security programs: how to block fake news?
85.	European Union and the Media: what are the interventions for media literacy?
86.	Young digital citizens: simple recipients or active participants?
87.	How useful is LinkedIn in terms of job search?
88.	Democracy and the risk of hacking: a legitimate fear?
89.	Why are there so few women in STEM?
90.	Big Data and Internet of things. What are the risks behind?
91.	Influencers Marketing: unlimited growth or 'bubble'?
92.	Why people use Tinder and other app dating?
93.	How did fake news manipulate information on the migration phenomenon?
94.	Information overload in the age of Social Media. How does it affect the accuracy of the information?
95.	Gender stereotype in Sport: where are we at?
96.	What is the role of Facebook affirmation towards ideal self-image and self-esteem?
97.	What are the differences between gender equity, gender equality and women's empowerment?
98.	Have Gender Stereotypes Changed Since the Mid-20th Century?
99.	How to fight bullying on Instagram?
100.	Which is the Social Media are affected by cyberbullying most?
101.	Are Social Media harmful to your health?
102.	Who share most fake information on Facebook?
103.	How is a fake news born and why they got clicked more than a real news?
104.	Are the companies pursuing who has more followers? And which message is important?
105.	How to make Digital participation inclusive?
106.	Here's the digital divide, in which side are you?
107.	How can online platforms affect a young person's personal development through self-image?
108.	Can an online developed self-image be dangerous for a young person?
109.	Is the online world increasing or reducing gender discrimination?
110.	Are women treated on social media differently than men?
111.	Who is working and in which ways to improve Internet safety and privacy?
112.	Will we be 100% safe on the internet in the future?
113.	Is it possible for young people to be offline for 1 week? And How about 40-50 year olds?
114.	How much time do we spend on average per day on a social platform? What are the differences between the European countries?
115.	How effective are fact-checking companies and how are people processing these

companies' recommendations?
116. When were the people better informed: in the past or nowadays?
117. How effective is digital activism? Which are the examples of how digital participation and activism can change something?
118. What are the best places for digital participation and why?
119. Direct or representative democracy. How can digital media change the institutional structure of our societies?
120. What is the right to oblivion and where did it come from?
121. Are Social Media sources of stress or dependence?
122. Can E-participation enhance urban planning?

Appendix 2: Research Projects Developed in Cycle 3

1. Homophobia
2. Stereotypes Online
3. Exploring Self Image
4. Banter, memes and influencers
5. Nomophobia Levels of Secondary School Students
6. Follow-Up as A Social Media Influencer (Tülay Göçimen)
7. The Impact of Social Media on the Tendency towards Depression
8. The Relationship Between the Use of Social Media and Narcissism
9. Social Impact on People: How Do You Feel Without Your Keyboard?
10. Don't stay silent: Investigation of the impact of a patriarchal society on women's social lives
11. Gender Inequality
12. The Best Female Characters in Literature
13. Changing the names of female characters in Turkish novels and stories between 1830-1960
14. The Image of Women Redefined in Didem Mamak's Poems: A Mother, Child and a Sorcerer
15. What Is Bullying
16. Bullying
17. The impact of time spent gaming on mathematical achievement
18. Technology across time
19. The impact of the use of technology on social relationships
20. What Would I Do?
21. Fire Sensor for the visually and hearing impaired
22. Gender Equality
23. The Impact of Migration on Society and The Opinions of Refugees: The Syrian Example
24. A Different View of Folk Songs: Women in Bursa
25. The Impact of Technology on Values (An Interaction Project)
26. The Impact of Migration on Communities and Individuals
27. Raising Awareness of Violence Against Children
28. Defining Future Jobs and Career Choices
29. Our lives and the lives of adults on Social Media
30. The Paris Principles in 14 images
31. Dictatorship
32. Consent/Permission
33. Cyberbullying
34. Hacking
35. Fake News
36. Self-Image
37. Anti-(Cyber)Bullying Strategy for the Centre of Inclusive Schools Vienna
38. Age limits and Online Gaming

39. How to be respectful online
40. Appearances Online
41. Internet Activities and Behaviours
42. Tech in the Class
43. Emojis to express ourselves
44. Online activities for 9 and 10 year olds
45. Awareness on of online dangers
46. Online appearances
47. What is digital activism? How can we get involved?
48. How do we become more educated to get reliable information?
49. Addressing our self-images on social media
50. Exposing surveillance culture and social media
51. Digital Addiction
52. Distinguishing between real and false information on the Internet ("Fake News")
53. Privacy on the web
54. Stereotypes on Social Networks
55. Gender stereotypes in education
56. Stereotypes and self-image
57. Stereotypes in sports
58. Gender gap in advertising
59. Cultural background and stereotypes
60. Stereotypes related to sexual orientation
61. Gender stereotypes during the childhood
62. Body positivity on Instagram and young women body-acceptance
63. Social media support people facing mental illness
64. Gender neutral environment in school
65. Increase gender equality to break down the barriers for women entrepreneurs
66. Empowering the youth to reduce the risk of cyberbullying
67. Online programmes to increase access to mental health care
68. Over-usage of cell phone is connected to increase in anxiety
69. Media literacy Youth Corp to bridge the digital divide among older population
70. The integration of Gamification approach in education for a better learning experience
71. Digital tools to improve the inclusivity of democracy
72. The rise of narcissism in influencers
73. The correlation between self-esteem and how we present ourselves online
74. The eradication of stereotypes thanks to education
75. The role gender and Disney princesses play
76. Stopping the spread of harmful behaviour towards teenagers online
77. The measures cybersecurity takes to protect the users and the system
78. The changes of personality in the world of influencer marketing
79. The stress created by the use of social media
80. Fake News and online security programmes

81. The interventions of the European Union in media literacy
82. The participation of young digital citizens
83. LinkedIn and professional apps for Job search: online presentation
84. Actions to increase online safety
85. Reasons for lack of female presence in STEM jobs
86. Internet of things and networks, opportunities and risks of a boundless world
87. The world of influencers. Marketing models, trend of the phenomenon and possible evolutions
88. Phenomenology of psychosocial influence of app dating
89. Migratory phenomenon vs. fake news. How public audience is influenced by wrong messages
90. Information and social media bombardment. How huge amounts of visual stimulation influence our brain
91. Gender stereotypes in sports. Anti-discrimination policies and the presence of women in various sport
92. Facebook affirmation and its role towards self-image and self-esteem
93. Differences among gender equity, gender equality and women's empowerment
94. The change in gender stereotype since Mid-20th Century
95. The problem of fight bullying on Instagram
96. Social Media and Cyberbullying: a comparative analysis
97. Social Media: risk and consequences on the health
98. Fake news on Facebook: analysis of the main players
99. The birth of fake news and why they get more views
100. Influencer marketing: companies, followers and content message
101. Digital Participation and its inclusiveness
102. Digital divide and its inequalities
103. A young person's self-image is directly affected by online platforms and thus jeopardising his/hers personal development
104. An online-developed self-image can be dangerous for a young person's self-esteem.
105. The online world is increasing gender discrimination.
106. Women are treated differently online than men.
107. The people and bodies behind our internet safety and privacy
108. Internet will never be 100% safe
109. Young people's and older generations' capability of not being online
110. The big amount of time young people across Europe spend online per day
111. People's perception on fake news spotters and their reliability
112. The quality of information throughout the decades
113. The effectiveness of digital activism to shape our future
114. The best place for digital participation
115. Direct democracy, as digital media change democratic institutions
116. Legal and factual considerations on the right to be forgotten
117. Social Media are sources of dependence
118. Potentialities of gamification in shaping urban infrastructures

References

- García-Holgado, A., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2018). *WYRED Platform, the ecosystem for the young people*. Paper presented at the HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA. <https://youtu.be/TRDjN5boky8>
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016). The WYRED project: A technological platform for a generative research and dialogue about youth perspectives and interests in digital society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 9(4), vi-x.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2017). WYRED Project. *Education in the Knowledge Society*, 18(3), 7-14. doi:10.14201/eks2017183714
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Durán-Escudero, J. (2017). Interaction design principles in WYRED platform. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Technology in Education. 4th International Conference, LCT 2017. Held as Part of HCI International 2017, Vancouver, BC, Canada, July 9–14, 2017. Proceedings, Part II* (pp. 371-381). Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & García-Holgado, A. (2019). WYRED, a platform to give young people the voice on the influence of technology in today's society. A citizen science approach. In K. O. Villalba-Condori, F. J. García-Peñalvo, J. Lavonen, & M. Zapata-Ros (Eds.), *Proceedings of the II Congreso Internacional de Tendencias e Innovación Educativa – CITIE 2018 (Arequipa, Perú, November 26-30, 2018)* (pp. 128-141). Aachen, Germany: CEUR-WS.org.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., García-Holgado, A., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., & Seoane-Pardo, A. M. (2018). Usability test of WYRED Platform. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Design, Development and Technological Innovation. 5th International Conference, LCT 2018, Held as Part of HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA, July 15-20, 2018, Proceedings, Part I* (pp. 73-84). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016)* (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., & García-Holgado, A. (2019). Study of the Usability of the WYRED Ecosystem Using Heuristic Evaluation. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Design, Experiences. 6th International Conference, LCT 2019, Held as Part of the 21st HCI International Conference, HCII 2019, Orlando, FL, USA, July 26–31, 2019. Proceedings, Part I* (pp. 50-63). Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., García-Holgado, A., & Seoane-Pardo, A. M. (2019). Analyzing the usability of the WYRED Platform with undergraduate students to improve its features. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 18(3), 455-468. doi:10.1007/s10209-019-00672-z
- Griffiths, D., Kearney, N. A., García-Peñalvo, F. J., Seoane-Pardo, A. M., Cicala, F., Gojkovic, T., . . . Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2017). *Children and Young People Today: Initial Insights from the WYRED Project*. European Union: WYRED Consortium. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/6unxmD>
- WYRED Consortium. (2017a). WYRED Research Cycle Infographic. European Union: WYRED Consortium.
- WYRED Consortium. (2017b). WYRED Research Cycle Overview Infographic. European Union: WYRED Consortium.
- WYRED Consortium. (2019). *WYRED Processes Handbook. WP1_D1.3*. Luxemburg: WYRED Consortium. Retrieved from <https://zenodo.org/record/3567914>